

Approximate solutions of linear Fredholm Integro-Differential equations system with variable coefficients

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Abstract

In this article, approximate solutions of linear Fredholm integro-differential equations (FIDEs) system with variable coefficients types by means of the hybrid-Bessel method is considered. The matrix equations correspond to a system of linear algebraic equations with the unknown Bessel-hybrid coefficients. Some examples are given, showing its effectiveness and convenience.

Keyword Bessel-hybrid functions, Fredholm, System of integro-differential equations.

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1 Introduction

Integro-differential and integral equations system have been found to various kinds of phenomena in science and engineering, such as glass-forming process, nano-hydrodynamics, drop wise condensation, and wind ripple in the desert [?],[?],[?],[?]. In this research, we try to introduce a solution of system of linear (FIDEs) with conditions, the following form:

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=1}^r p_{ij}^k(x) y_j^{(k)}(x) = g_i(x) + \sum_{j=1}^r \xi_{ij}^f \int_a^b k_{ij}^f(x, t) y_j(t) dt, \quad (1)$$

$$0 \leq a \leq x, t \leq b, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r,$$

$$y_j^{(k)}(a) = y_{ik}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1.$$

where $y_j(t), j = 1, 2, \dots, r$ are an unknown functions, the known functions are $p_{ij}^k(x), k = 0, 1, \dots, n, g_i(x), k_{ij}(x, t), i, j = 1, 2, \dots, r$. Also, ξ_{ij}^f, ξ_{ij}^v and y_{ik} are real or complex constants.

2 Basic properties

2.1 Bessel-hybrid functions

Bessel-hybrid functions $b(n, m, x)$ have three arguments n, m and x . Respectively, n is the order for block-pulse [?], m is the order for $J_{m, M}(x)$, truncated Bessel polynomials of first

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kind, which is defined in [?] and x is the normalized time, is defined on the interval $[0, 1)$ as:

$$b(n, m, x) = \begin{cases} J_{m,M}(Nx - n + 1), & \frac{n-1}{N} \leq x < \frac{n}{N}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

2.2 Transformation matrix basis and function approximation

Now, we can expanded a function $y_j(x)$ in $L^2(0, 1)$ space in Bessel-hybrid functions as

$$y_j(x) \simeq A_j^T B(x), \quad A_j = [a_{10}^j, \dots, a_{1M}^j, \dots, a_{N0}^j, \dots, a_{NM}^j]^T, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r, \quad (3)$$

where A_j and $B(x) = [b(1, 0, x), \dots, b(1, M, x), \dots, b(N, 0, x), \dots, b(N, M, x)]^T$ are constant coefficients and basis vectors of Bessel-hybrid functions. Also, we can transform the Bessel-hybrid functions to M-th degree Taylor basis functions, which is defined in [?] as:

$$B(x) = D\hat{X}(x), \quad (4)$$

by substituting Eq. (4) in Eq. (3), we get

$$y_j(x) \simeq A_j^T D\hat{X}(x) = \hat{X}^T(x) D^T A_j \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r. \quad (5)$$

3 Fundamental Relations and Solution Method

3.1 Matrix relation for the differential part

In this section, we obtain approximation to the k-th derivative of $y_j(x), j = 1, 2, \dots, r$, by using Eqs. (4) and (5), we have [?]:

$$y_j^{(k)}(x) \simeq (\hat{X}^{(k)}(x))^T D^T A_j = \hat{X}^T(x) (\hat{B}^k)^T D^T A_j, \quad k = 0, \dots, n, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, r. \quad (6)$$

According to Eq. (6), by using nodal points of Newton-Cotes in [?], we have

$$E_i(x_s) \simeq \sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=1}^r p_{ij}^k(x_s) \hat{X}^T(x_s) (\hat{B}^k)^T D^T A_j, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r. \quad (7)$$

Or in general

$$EA = \sum_{k=0}^n P_k \bar{X} (\bar{B})^k \bar{D} A, \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} P_k &= \text{diag}(P^k(x_1), P^k(x_2), \dots, P^k(x_{N(M+1)})), & \bar{B} &= \text{diag}(\hat{B}^T, \hat{B}^T, \dots, \hat{B}^T), \\ \bar{X} &= \text{diag}(\hat{X}^T(x_1), \hat{X}^T(x_2), \dots, \hat{X}^T(x_{N(M+1)})), & \bar{D} &= \text{diag}(\hat{D}^T, \hat{D}^T, \dots, \hat{D}^T), \\ P^k(x) &= [p_{ij}^k(x)], & A &= [A_1, A_2, \dots, A_r]^T, \quad i, j = 0, 1, \dots, r. \end{aligned}$$

3.2 Matrix relation for the Fredholm integral part

We approximate kernel function $k_{ij}^f(x, t), i, j = 1, 2, \dots, r$, by the truncated Maclaurin series and truncated Bessel-hybrid series, which is defined in [?]

$$k_{ij}^f(x, t) = \hat{X}^T(x)_t k_{ij}^f \hat{X}(t), \quad k_{ij}^f(x, t) = B^T(x)_b k_{ij}^f B(t), \quad (9)$$

by using the Eqs. (5) and (9) in Fredholm integral part of Eq. (1), we get

$$\int_0^1 k_{ij}^f(x, t) y_j(t) dt \simeq \int_0^1 B^T(x)_b k_{ij}^f B(t) B^T(t) A_j dt = B^T(x)_b k_{ij}^f Q_f A_j, \quad (10)$$

where $Q_f = D\hat{H}_f D^T$ and $\hat{H}_f$ is defined in [?]. We have matrix form of Fredholm integral part

$$F_i(x_s) = \hat{X}^T(x_s) D^T {}_b k_{ij}^f Q_f A_j,$$

consequently, we have

$$FA = \bar{X} \bar{D} k_f \bar{Q}_f A, \quad k_f = [{}_b k_{ij}^f], \quad i, j = 0, 1, \dots, r, \quad \bar{Q}_f = \text{diag}(Q_f, Q_f, \dots, Q_f). \quad (11)$$

3.3 Method of solution

To solve Eq. (1) with conditions, we substituting Eqs. (8) and (11) in Eq. (1) as

$$\begin{aligned} EA = G + FA, \quad G &= [g_1(x_1), g_2(x_2), \dots, g_r(x_{N(M+1)})]^T, \\ (E - F)A &= WA = G. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Now, we used Eq. (6) to obtain the matrix form of initial conditions, so that

$$\hat{X}^T(a) (\hat{B}^k)^T D^T A_j = y_{ik}, \quad i, j = 1, \dots, r, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1, \quad (13)$$

or briefly,

$$\bar{X}_a \bar{B} \bar{D} A = Y_k, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1, \quad \bar{X}_a = \text{diag}(\hat{X}^T(a), \hat{X}^T(a), \dots, \hat{X}^T(a)). \quad (14)$$

Consequently, we can write the fundamental matrix equations for initial conditions as

$$U_k A = Y_k, \quad U_k = \bar{X}_a \bar{B} \bar{D}, \quad Y_k = [y_{1k}, y_{2k}, \dots, y_{rk}]^T, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, n-1. \quad (15)$$

Ultimately, we are replacing the rows of U by last rows of W and the rows of Y_k by last rows of G to obtain the solution of Eq. (1) under conditions. We obtain A from system and by substituting A_j in Eq. (6), we get approximate solution.

$$\hat{W}A = \hat{G}.$$

4 Illustrative examples

We report the results of some examples given in the different papers. In addition, express absolute error function which is defined as $|y_j(x) - y_{jN}(x)|$ where $y_j(x)$ is the exact solution of Eq. (1) and $y_{jN}(x)$ is the approximate of $y_j(x)$. All the examples were performed on the computer by means of a program written in MATLAB.

Example 4.1. Consider system of the linear FIDEs given in [?] and [?],

$$\begin{cases} y_1''(x) = \frac{3}{10}x + 6 - \int_0^1 (2xy_1(t) - 6xy_2(t))dt, \\ y_2''(x) = 15x + \frac{4}{5} - \int_0^1 (3(2x + t^2)y_1(t) - 6(2x + t^2)y_2(t))dt, \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

with the conditions $y_1(0) = 1$, $y_1'(0) = 0$, $y_2(0) = -1$ and $y_2'(0) = 2$. Now, for $N = 2$, $M = 3$, according to the proposed method, we obtain the exact solution of Eq. (16).

Example 4.2. Consider the following system of the linear FIDE [?]

$$\begin{cases} y_1''(x) - xy_2'(x) - y_1(x) = (x-2)\sin(x) + \int_0^1 (x\cos(t)y_1(t) - x\sin(t)y_2(t))dt, \\ y_2''(x) - 2xy_1'(x) + y_2(x) = -2x\cos(x) + \int_0^1 (\sin(x)\cos(t)y_1(t) - \sin(x)\cos(t)y_2(t))dt, \end{cases}$$

with the conditions $y_1(0) = 0$, $y_1'(0) = 1$, $y_2(0) = 1$ and $y_2'(0) = 0$, the exact solutions are $y_1(x) = \sin(x)$ and $y_2(x) = \cos(x)$. The maximum absolute errors for different N and M are shown in Table 1. The values obtained show that if N and M increase, the accuracy will increase.

Table 1: Maximum absolute errors of Example 4.2.

M	N	$e(y_1)$	$e(y_2)$
3	2	4.32×10^{-2}	1.02×10^{-1}
3	3	1.36×10^{-3}	1.51×10^{-2}
3	4	9.87×10^{-4}	8.98×10^{-3}

Conclusion

The aim of this paper is to develop hybrid-Bessel method for obtaining the solutions of linear systems of FIDEs. One significant advantage of this method is that with the increasing values of N and M, approximate solution is convergent and the accuracy is increased sufficiently. Illustrative examples are included to demonstrate that the method is a very effective and useful technique for finding approximate solutions of these systems.

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